

IPERION HS

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Interim report on documentation of instrument parameters and analysis protocols across access platforms, and metadata requirements

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1 Glossary, Abbreviations and Acronyms

Note: The first use of these terms in the main text of these terms are *italicised*.

BALaT	“Belgium's art history in a single click, more than 750.000 downloadable photos”. http://balat.kikirpa.be/
CIDOC	ICOM International Committee for Documentation (https://cidoc.mini.icom.museum/)
CIDOC CRM	The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) is a standard ontology developed for the Heritage domain. (https://www.cidoc-crm.org/)
Data	“In the pursuit of knowledge, data ... is a collection of discrete units of information in a conceptual model that in their most basic forms convey quantity, quality, fact, statistics, or other basic units of meaning. “ (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data)
DMP	Data Management Plan - For IPERION HS, the Data Management Plan (DMP) documents the agreed data management procedures and protocols used ... to organise, preserve and share data produced during the IPERION HS project. (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4541266)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier. A DOI is a persistent identifier used to uniquely identify various objects., which is standardised by the ISO. (https://www.doi.org)
EDX	Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy – “an analytical technique used for the elemental analysis or chemical characterization of a sample” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Energy-dispersive_X-ray_spectroscopy)
Elasticsearch	“Elasticsearch is a search engine ... It provides a distributed, multitenant-capable full-text search engine with an HTTP web interface and schema-free JSON documents ...” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elasticsearch
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science http://www.e-rihs.eu
E-RIHS.be	The Belgium national hub or E-RIHS.
EU H2020	“Horizon 2020 was the EU's research and innovation funding programme from 2014-2020 with a budget of nearly €80 billion.” (https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-2020_en)
FAIR	Provide guidelines related to improving the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital resources (https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/)
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fourier-transform_infrared_spectroscopy)
GC-MS	Gas Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gas_chromatography%E2%80%93mass_spectrometry)
GitHub	An open, online software repository and development platform. (https://github.com)
HESCIDA	Heritage Science Data Archive, an infrastructure project of E-RIHS.be (2019 - 2023) with the aim of developing a national DIGILAB repository. The project is led by KIK/IRPA and funded by the Belgian Science Policy Office (http://hescida.kikirpa.be)
HSI	Hyperspectral Imaging (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hyperspectral_imaging)
Interoperability	Data interoperability in a broader sense means that data in diverse formats and from different locations or provenance can be unified, integrated or used together. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interoperability , see also https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/)
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science, EU funded H2020 project (https://www.iperionhs.eu)
IRUG	Infrared & Raman Users Group (http://www.irug.org)
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry: a federation of National Adhering Organizations working for the advancement of the chemical sciences, especially by developing nomenclature and terminology

JavaScript	“JavaScript ... often abbreviated JS, is a programming language that is one of the core technologies of the World Wide Web ...” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JavaScript
JCAMP-DX	An open, human readable file format for data exchange (DX) in chemistry, originally developed by the Joint Committee on Atomic and Molecular Physical Data (JCAMP). IUPAC took over the responsibility of maintaining and extending the JCAMP-DX standards from JCAMP in 1995. https://iupac.org/what-we-do/digital-standards/jcamp-dx
JSON	JSON (which stands for JavaScript Object Notation) is an open standard file format developed for the exchange of digital data. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JSON)
JSON Schema	JSON Schema is a vocabulary that allows you to annotate and validate JSON documents. JSON Schema is a vocabulary that allows one to define, annotate and validate JSON documents.
KIK/IRPA	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage in Brussels, Belgium (Dutch: Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium; French: Institut royale du Patrimoine artistique; https://www.kikirpa.be)
Metadata	“Metadata is data that provides information about other data, but not the content of the data, such as the text of a message or the image itself.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Metadata)
MFT	Microfading Testing (MFT) is an analytical technique used to determine an object’s light sensitivity. It is a method for assessing the vulnerability of individual museum objects to light-fading, including those for which the identity of the colourant is unknown.
MIT licence	“The MIT Licence is a permissive free software licence originating at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIT_License) - https://choosealicense.com/licenses/mit/
Ontology	“In computer science and information science, an ontology encompasses a representation, formal naming, and definition of the categories, properties, and relations between the concepts, data, and entities that substantiate one, many, or all domains of discourse. “ (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ontology_(information_science)) - For examples see section 7.
Open Access	“Open access (OA) is a set of principles and a range of practices through which research outputs are distributed online, free of access charges or other barriers.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_access)
Open Data	Fully “Open data is data that is openly accessible, exploitable, editable and shared by anyone for any purpose, even commercially. Open data is licensed under an open licence.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_data)
P/S	Palmitate to stearate ratio: an often-used metric in GC-MS in which the ratio of the peak areas (or heights) of palmitic methyl ester and stearic methyl ester are used to determine the origin of the oil medium.
Paradata	“The paradata of a data set or survey are data about the process by which the data were collected” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Paradata)
PARTHENOS	“Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies” http://www.parthenos-project.eu , which was funded by European Commission under the “H2020 – EU.1.4.1.1. – Developing new world-class research infrastructures”.
Raman (Spectroscopy)	“... is a spectroscopic technique typically used to determine vibrational modes of molecules” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Raman_spectroscopy)
RDF	Resource Description Framework (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Resource_Description_Framework)
Semantic	Semantics “is the study of reference, meaning, or truth. “ (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semantics) - In relation to this work Semantic Data can be described as data that has been described and categorised in relation to a formal ontology.
SSHOC	The Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud, EU funded H2020 project (https://www.sshopencloud.eu/)
SSHOCro	“The SSHOC Reference Ontology proposes an ontological model and RDF Schema to be used as a top-level ontology for organizing knowledge and information found distributed across various primary sources of information...” (https://isl.ics.forth.gr/SSHOCro/)
T6.3	Task 6.3 “Interoperability of instrumentation and digital documentation”, from Work-package 6 of

	the IPERION HS EU funded H2020 project.
VJSF	Vuetify JSON Schema Forms: an open source library for generating webforms based on the JSON schema standard, based on the Vue and Vuetify frameworks (source code: https://github.com/koumoul-dev/vuetify-jsonschema-form , documentation: https://koumoul-dev.github.io/vuetify-jsonschema-form/latest)
Vocabulary	“Controlled vocabularies provide a way to organize knowledge for subsequent retrieval ...” they “...mandate the use of predefined, authorised terms ...” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Controlled_vocabulary) - such as the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat) or even extracts from Wikidata (https://www.wikidata.org).
XRF	X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy
Zenodo	Zenodo is an open, free, catch-all data repository supported by CERN (https://home.cern), OpenAire (https://www.openaire.eu) and the EU Horizon 2020 Programme (https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020) – For more details see: https://zenodo.org .

2 Abstract

This Milestone is an interim report of the activities carried out within IPERION HS Task 6.3 (Interoperability of instrumentation and digital documentation in IPERION HS). It provides an update of the description of the task and a clear definition of its scope. It also describes the three main areas of work: the Data Management plan for IPERION HS, identifying tools for metadata capture and presentation, and the development of a practical approach to the modelling the capture of the metadata required to achieve an appropriate level of interoperability. In addition the report proposes an as yet theoretical definition of eight levels of potential interoperability between IPERION HS collections, describes the six proposed stages for the definition and documentation of appropriate metadata for a given examination or analysis, presents the series of metadata models created so far, and provides a detailed descriptions of the tools used. The report also outlines plans for the remainder of the Task as well as presenting a short series of recommendations for future work.

3 Introduction

T6.3 is focused on the *interoperability* of the research work carried out across *IPERION HS* and the *data, metadata* and *paradata* it produces. The purpose of this is to ensure that examinations of our heritage carried out at different times, at different locations, and by different people can be put in context, trusted, and efficiently and appropriately compared with other relevant work. This work is being carried out to help ensure that the research carried out within *IPERION HS* is *FAIR* (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).

Figure 1: FAIR Data Principles: Image taken from The Open Science Training Handbook - https://open-science-training-handbook.github.io/Open-Science-Training-Handbook_EN/02OpenScienceBasics/02OpenResearchDataAndMaterials.html

Making data interoperable relates to ensuring the appropriate use of common formats and standards, and linking, describing and categorising data with agreed ontological systems and terms which are documented within open controlled vocabularies. This document will outline the work that has been carried out with T6.3 and outline the plans for future activities, exploring practical approaches to interoperability, defining what metadata and paradata is required to achieve acceptable levels of interoperability and identifying and developing appropriate tools and procedures to help researchers gather and document their instrument parameters, analysis protocols and research data. The objective is to adopt a common general approach to modelling documentation schemes, using standard metadata structures to capture a realistic and useful level of metadata, defined by experts of each technique. This work aims to enable interoperability of procedures and proper exchange of information and comparable data without necessarily adopting similar analytical protocols or similar instrumental setups.

3.1 Levels of Interoperability

A standard digital approach to interoperability is to identify all the key pieces of metadata needed to define and describe a dataset and then map them to one or more domain standard *ontologies* and controlled *vocabularies*, to organise how the data is classified, defined, and linked together in a standard way. If everyone maps their own metadata to the same standard structure, services could automatically aggregate and combine the then interoperable data, from multiple sources, and present access to it via a single interface. However, although this approach will create interoperable knowledge it does not necessarily always create fully interoperable raw data, as the “exact” values produced can be unique to a given equipment setup and procedure. Consideration needs to be given to what data can usefully be made interoperable to maximise its exploitability and reuse. One of the first pieces of work carried out within T6.3 was to begin to define some of the possible different levels of interoperability in relation to the field of Heritage Science. These draft levels have been proposed as a starting point for the work of T6.3 and are intended to help stimulate further discussion. These levels should be seen as indicators of some of the key aspects or features of interoperable Heritage Science data. Table 1 presents a proposed set of levels, along with examples of the types of questions each level of interoperability might be able to answer. At this time these levels should be seen as aspirational rather than a description of current best practice, as very few, if any, institutions can be described as fully compliant with these levels of interoperability, for their full collections.

Level	Description	Typical questions
1	Standardised collection records – published as linkable data.	What objects do you all have? Which collections include works by Raphael?
2	Shared, <i>open access</i> , definitions of analytical techniques and processes. Augment collection records with yes/no flag against available technique types .	Which objects have been X-rayed? Which objects have undergone media analysis?
3	Provide more detailed descriptions of techniques , including equipment with documented protocols – published as linkable data.	What <i>XRF</i> equipment has been used to examine objects? Who has used a Zeiss Evo MA10 SEM?
4	Shared, open access, definitions of Heritage Science materials and equipment . Augment collections records with keywords and categories based on agreed controlled vocabularies .	Which collections have identified bitumen in paint samples? Who is studying the degradation of smalt?
5	Shared, open access, definitions of data processing and interpretation standards , by technique. Augment collections records with new metadata fields related to the interpretation standards.	Who has been characterising the condition of cellulose nitrate coatings using <i>FTIR</i> , following a standard procedure? Who is confirming the presence of binding media by <i>GC-MS</i> , via <i>P/S</i> ratios?

6	<p>Full semantic description of augmented collections records. Full semantic descriptions of analytical procedures and data formats. Open access FAIR datasets stored in public data repositories.</p>	<p>How do my Hyperspectral Imaging (<i>HSI</i>) results of 19th century paintings compare with the results of HSIs recorded for 17th century Italian paintings kept in Spanish collections since the early 19th century?</p>
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Table 1. A series of theoretical levels of interoperability presented within the early stages of the work.

3.2 What does data mean?

“The main class of data, being considered under IPERION HS, will be raw and interpreted data created and or processed, relating to the technical or analytical examination of Heritage works, by the access providers working within IPERION HS and by any other research activities carried out in the framework of the project. However, the notion of “IPERION HS data” also covers a wider range of digital assets, including publications, reports, survey data, documentation, software and more.”¹

Within this report three related terms will be used; “data”, “metadata” and “paradata”. Data can be taken as quite a broad term, relating to any, at least semi organised, sets of information, which can be described, defined and used. This can include a wide range of things from raw analytical data to annotations on an image. For this data to have real meaning it needs to be appropriately described, categorised or tagged. Now metadata is a sub class of data that generally provides that meaning, defining specific pieces of information about other “things” (Objects, Events, People, Experiments, etc), their titles, descriptions, heights, etc. Metadata is used to connect or group similar things together, providing meaning and context and allowing search and discovery. Paradata is a sub-class of metadata that is used to describe the processes through which other data sets have been gathered, such as a method statement for an experiment or the documented procedures followed while carrying out a survey.

3.3 Metadata Models

Metadata modelling relates to the examination and definition of the rules and relationships relevant to the construction of a specific model of knowledge. Followed by the optional creation of graphical presentations of the agreed rules and relationships. Within this task, as outlined in section 4, the work has initially focused on capturing the language and relationships used by domain experts to describe their own areas of expertise, but still informed by the more complex ontologies and resources described in section 7. The metadata models considered within T6.3 represent a range of simpler, generic, reusable, shared concepts such as objects, projects, examinations, etc. which can be defined once but referenced again and again, and a smaller selection of detailed models capturing the full complexity of the metadata required to describe specific experiments/technical examinations. Where possible these more complex models should mimic, exploit, or reference any existing metadata models, standards or schemas developed for a given technique. These more complex models are intended to act as a guide or template for how other Heritage Science work can be modelled with the aim that in the future such models can be created for all services offered

¹ Padfield, Joseph. (2021). D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788560>

within the IPERION HS catalogue of services.² This would help ensure that the data gathered in relation to specific techniques across different institutions and countries can follow the same core, interoperable foundations. Where applicable, multiple versions of given models can be kept to document how they have evolved and developed over time. An example of an initial draft model for a generic piece of equipment can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: A very simple example metadata model indicating some of the generic metadata required to describe a given piece of equipment. Please note this particular model is not intended to document the experimental conditions of a given experiment, this will be captured in a separate model. This draft equipment model and subsequent development work is documented on GitHub (<https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/Shared%20Models>)

The purpose of developing or identifying these metadata models is to ensure that we can have a consistent, standard, and interoperable way of describing the metadata required to describe the work carried out within IPERION HS and the future E-RIHS initiative.

A diagram indicating the range of model types currently being considered and how they could be connected has been included in Figure 3. Developing models for all these concepts and obviously all the techniques listed in the current IPERION HS catalogue of services is beyond the scope of this individual task, but it has been developed to help indicate how the work begun in this task needs to be developed and implemented going forward.

² <https://www.iperionhs.eu/catalogue-of-services/>

Figure 3: This diagram represents the range of generic metadata models currently being considered and how they can be connected to each other.

4 Overall Work Plan

The initial plan for T6.3 had been to concentrate on exploring “Level 6” interoperability for a limited number of techniques; such as environmental data and spectral imaging data.

However, this work can be quite complex for non-specialists to follow, requiring a combination of domain experts and knowledge/semantic experts and can be a difficult starting point for researchers new to this area of work. Therefore, more practical, inclusive approaches to achieving interoperability were considered. Discussions between the task participants and the wider IPERION HS community made it clear that it would be more appropriate and more inclusive to focus on a practical approach to interoperability, rather than a semantic one. Therefore, the work of the task has progressed on a more hands-on basis, beginning by capturing the existing knowledge of relevant domain experts, converting it into agreed metadata and paradata, and developing controlled, consistent, and efficient methods of capturing this data to foster future interoperability.

The two aims of this approach were to examine the questions:

- How easy can we make it for researchers to define and gather all the metadata and paradata required to fully capture the context as well as the meaning of their work?
- How easy can we make it for researchers to publish their data to ensure that it can be done in a FAIR manner to support future re-use?

To begin to answer these questions the work within T6.3 was organised into three main areas:

- Developing a core *DMP* for IPERION-HS (Deliverable D6.1) based on a consideration of the FAIR principles, see section 5 - including the development of practical workflow diagrams see section 5.1.
- Identifying and demonstrating an appropriate set of simple, open tools to practically model and gather metadata for researchers see section 6.1 and section 6.2.
- Working with domain experts to define a practical process for modelling and capturing the key metadata required to describe the context and meaning of their work, see section 9.

4.1 Practical Data Modelling for Interoperability

For IPERION HS, when considering the hundreds of specialists and researchers involved, spread across multiple countries, a consistent approach to digital documentation needs to be open, easy to edit and share, and be flexible enough to integrate with a range of current and future systems.

Where possible, efforts were also made to exploit existing solutions and systems to avoid the classic issues of duplicating effort. Also, to ensure that required data only needs to be gathered once, again avoiding duplicated effort, the areas of documentation or data gathering are being broken up into reusable, linkable modules, such as Projects, Objects, People, Equipment, Methods, Actual Experiments, etc. As each of these resultant modules are considered, a series of stages, described in Table 2, are being followed to develop the interoperability of the data gathered and produced. These data gathering stages do not directly map to the defined levels of Interoperability, in Table 1, but areas of overlap will be indicated. The scope of this task specifically covers stages 1-5. Examples of this work will be described in section 3.3.

#	Stage	Comments
1	Draft the unique scope or model of a given activity.	To improve efficiency, the definitions are broken up into discrete modules or models - one only needs to define a project once, not every time and examination is carried out within said project.
2	List the required metadata and paradata.	Working with domain experts to define what data and documentation is needed to fully document their work and any results they produce - exploiting a process based on spreadsheets developed in <i>PARTHENOS</i> .
3	Create a simple graphical model of the activity	Visual representations provide a clear visualisation of the required data relationships for a given model - related models can also be connected to validate the gathered data.
4	Identify how the model links to other models, controlled vocabularies and external data sources.	Linking to external vocabularies and data sources ensures improved interoperability through the usage of shared terms and language. Linking models to each other increases efficiency by removing the need for duplicating shared data for similar data gathering activities. This stage directly relates to the interoperability levels 1-5.
5	Convert the model and links into a form template for data input.	Automatically generating data entry forms based on open templates ensures that forms can be evaluated and updated, as required, without the need for additional development work.
6	Integrate the template into a general data gathering system	Storing the gathered data within a shared data store, rather than as separate documents, facilitates the reuse of the data and dynamic referencing between data sets. It could also allow the generation of dynamic automated reports in relation to the work being carried out, such as all the
7	Evaluate the data gathering process and the	This work also includes comparing similar models ensuring, where possible, that the models are consistent and that all

	gathered data and then improve the process as required.	the required data is being gathered.
8	Semantically model the gathered data in relation to standard domain ontologies such as the <i>CIDOC CRM</i>	This work can be done at a later stage to improve searching and organisation of the gathered data. It will also increase the potential of further connecting the gathered data to other semantically defined resources. This stage directly relates to the interoperability level 6.

Table 2: The eight stages of work identified for practical data modelling within T6.3

To support the accessibility of the work done, along with its reusability and interoperability, easily accessible and open formats were used throughout the process. Beginning with simple text documents and spreadsheets at the initial data gathering and modelling stages, followed by the use of *JSON* formatted text documents and templates in the data gathering and recording stages. The *JSON* format was selected to perform this work as it is well documented, widely used and even human readable, while still being designed to be easily machine readable. *JSON* documents can also be easily stored and searched via systems such as *Elasticsearch* or even directly ingested into bespoke documentation systems. There are also a number of existing tools to simplify the process of working with *JSON* documents and automatically processing *JSON* templates to create user-friendly data gathering forms, see section 6.2.

The use of simple formats and domain specific language to create these initial models and data gathering forms greatly lowers the barriers for involvement for less technical researchers. It can also be said that although the process was still relatively complex the first few times it was done, as more and more examples are completed it will become easier and easier to simply edit and update existing examples to create new models and templates. Another benefit of this open process is that final data gathering systems will be based on open, editable *JSON* templates, thus allowing updates and changes to be made to the forms and format of the gathered data, without the need for extensive development work to alter or update the documentation systems themselves.

As indicated in stage 8, more complex semantic descriptions of the data gathered or the relationships between them can be integrated into the process at a later stage, by mapping the defined and agreed models to the appropriate standard ontologies.

4.2 *GitHub* as the Task Repository

To ensure that the process of the work carried out within this Task could be as FAIR as the data we plan to capture, an open repository was required to store and present the models and documents produced. This was to ensure that in addition to collaborating with other researchers within IPERION HS we would also be able to collaborate with the wider *E-RIHS* and Heritage Science communities as well as other relevant technical specialists. *GitHub* was selected as it provided a well-documented repository, developed to facilitate the dynamic development of digital files, complete with all the required administration functions to control user access and support online comments and discussion in relation to the presented models.

A dedicated *GitHub* repository was set up for the task to store files and discuss the work carried out.³ Separate folders were set up for each type or group of models as they were developed. The

³ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability>

work was documented by recording the simple tab-separated text documents and images to describe each version of each model generated, complete with a simple documentation file listing and describing all the included versions of each model as they are developed, see Figure 4. Further folders will be added to document the further outputs as the task develops.

Object Simple Model

Relates to models: Actor, Event

Date	Author	Version	Link	Comment
20-10-2021	J Padfield	1.0	LINK	Creation of the first draft example of a simple object model, based on the Parthenos spreadsheet
21-10-2021	J Padfield	1.1	LINK	Creation of V1.1, added in formatting to improve the clarity of the model and along with increased details of the included fields

Figure 4: An example simple model table, showing versions of the Object model, taken from GitHub (<https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/Shared%20Models>) – a live link to the latest version is included in section 8.

5 The IPERION-HS Data Management Plan (DMP)

The DMP, produced within this task, is an agreed set of data management procedures and protocols that can be used by the project partners to organise, preserve and share data produced during the IPERION HS project. It aims to ensure that all the data and processes, produced within IPERION HS, are as open and FAIR as possible, but also as closed as necessary. The DMP is intended to begin to help researchers answer these questions:

- What do we mean by IPERION HS data?
- What does “publishing data” mean?
- What are the FAIR principles?
- What are we required to do?
- How do we use it?

The IPERION-HS DMP is based on previous DMPs developed for *EU H2020* documents, specifically the DMPs for *SSHOC*⁴ and the earlier project *PARTHENOS*.⁵ The full IPERION-HS DMP is 40 pages long, however the main section of the document is only 12 pages, with an example IPERION HS Researcher DMP Template corresponding to a further 17 pages.

Version 1.0 of the DMP for IPERION HS was finished in January 2021 and delivered as “D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS”.⁶ This version covers generic issues across the whole project

⁴ <https://sshopencloud.eu/d16-sshoc-data-management-plan>

⁵ <https://www.parthenos-project.eu/portal/dmp>

⁶ Padfield, Joseph. (2021). D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788560>. The latest current version will always be found at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4541266>

although it may need to be updated during the project to include more granular details and developments relating to specific techniques and procedures.

On a practical basis the DMP is intended to aid the process of documenting all the data created and or used during each access to IPERION HS facilities/services or during each piece of work within the project. The DMP is also intended to describe how the collections of data and its relevant documentation can then be packaged up and published in an *open data* repository. Although other repositories can be used the default open data repository for IPERION HS is *Zenodo*⁷ and the published datasets are gathered in a dedicated “community” for IPERION HS.⁸

The main areas to consider can be summarised as:

- Gather all the required metadata, procedural documents/method statements and equipment details
- Confirm all the required publication licences for the gathered data
- Complete any reports, publications or deliverables
- Gather all the relevant data, descriptions, and references together in an agreed format
- Publish the data through Zenodo (or equivalent data repository)
- If not already done so via Zenodo, register the details of the published data with the IPERION HS Coordination Office.

5.1 Data Management Workflows

After the publication of the DMP, to further assist the data management work within IPERION HS, work began to summarise the information presented within the DMP in the form of data management workflows, which begins to map out the various stages of the IPERION HS data lifecycle, see Figure 5, with a simplified version in Figure 6, creating a visual guide for researchers within IPERION-HS. This workflow will continue to develop, as required, based on the work within T6.3 and the IPERON HS project.

⁷ Zenodo is an open, free, catch-all data repository supported by CERN (<https://home.cern>), OpenAire (<https://www.openaire.eu>) and the EU Horizon 2020 Programme (<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020>) – For more details see: <https://zenodo.org>.

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/communities/871034/?page=1&size=20>

Figure 5: The IPERION HS - DMP Workflow Diagram V1.2 - The high resolution version can be seen at: <https://research-ng-london.org.uk/ss-ihs/> and the model is further documented at: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/DMP> - The section on "Research or Access" has been expanded to provide a clearer example within this document.

Figure 6: A simplified version of the IPERION HS - DMP Workflow Diagram V1.1a - The model is further documented at: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/DMP>

6 Selecting and developing tools

Where possible, to support the sustainability and accessibility of the work carried out within T6.3, open-source tools and procedures have been selected or developed.

6.1 The Dynamic Modeller

To facilitate the live, virtual, collaborative development of the metadata models and their subsequent documentation, a key part of T6.3, a dynamic online modelling tool was developed.⁹ This tool automatically creates flow diagrams directly from simple tab separated sets of data, wrapped up into a simple user interface.¹⁰ The tool's simple GUI is split into two sections, see Figure 7; one for the tab separated text and one for the resultant model, with a simple "refresh" button provided to update the model as the text is edited. The system was set up to facilitate modelling discussions during online meetings, with one user sharing the screen and editing the text as required. However, after using the system for a while an even easier, more inclusive mode of use was identified, and the code was updated to allow users to copy and paste text¹¹ directly from online collaborative spreadsheets. In addition to the default styling users can also select from a range of predefined shapes and colours to enhance the generated models.¹²

Figure 7: A screenshot of the landing page for the Dynamic Modeller diagram tool – <https://research.ng-london.org.uk/modelling/> - displaying the default diagram which documents what the tool can do and the text inputs used to create it.

The Dynamic Modelling tool and its documentation have been specifically designed to make the generated models and the process for creating them as FAIR as is practicable:

⁹ The development of this tool was a collaborative effort spread across this and several other projects, including the EU Horizon 2020 funded SSHOC - Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (823782) (<https://sshopencloud.eu/>), along with work carried out to support the Linked.Art project (<https://linked.art/>).

¹⁰ The live version of this system can be found at: <https://research.ng-london.org.uk/modelling>.

¹¹ Rows and columns copied from spreadsheets are automatically formatted as tab separated data when then they are pasted into other text-based systems.

¹² A fourth tab separated value is used to indicate the required formatting - all the currently available options can be seen at: https://research.ng-london.org.uk/modelling/?example=example_formats

- The raw text/data used to create a model can be shared as a spreadsheet, simple text or even as a formatted compressed “bookmark” link to automatically populate the tool.
- The models themselves can be easily shared as PNG or SVG images.
- The code for the system itself has been published on GitHub and is freely available¹³ under a defined open license¹⁴ and is built using open and freely available software libraries.¹⁵
- The whole system has also been uploaded to the data repository Zenodo, which allocates the system its own DOI¹⁶ for citations and referencing.
- To further increase the systems accessibility, it has also been published in the SSHOC Marketplace.¹⁷

6.2 Metadata Templates formatted as JSON Documents

JSON is an open standard file format developed for the exchange of digital data. Though designed to be a machine-readable text format, JSON is also human readable, but it is not really a format intended to be created directly by most (human) researchers. The types of information; strings, numbers, dates, etc. expected within a specific JSON document can be defined using the JSON schema vocabulary. This combination provides a perfect sustainable solution for capturing and storing complex Heritage Science data as the content and its structure can be stored in one open exchangeable document that can be opened and used by many other pieces of software. Another benefit is that the same structure can be used to create empty templates that describe the agreed fields and data types required to define a given project, object, experiment, etc.¹⁸ To make the process even easier, a number of open-source software libraries exist that can translate a JSON schema template automatically into a form embedded in a website, for data entry. These forms, when filled in, can then subsequently export the entered fields as JSON data. In-built form validation also guarantees that this data is compliant with the schema outlined in the template. These open-source software libraries can be included in a range of different existing or future systems, from data gathering prototypes, as planned within this task, to integrated digital documentation systems developed for different large or small institutions. Thus, providing an open sustainable solution that can be used collaboratively across the Heritage Science domain without requiring everyone to use a specific piece of documentation software.

In this project, two solutions based on two different open-source libraries have been considered as possible solutions for developing this approach to using JSON schema templates and visualising them as web forms:

6.2.1 JSON Editor Demo tool

JSON Editor¹⁹ is a framework-agnostic *JavaScript* library for generating forms from JSON schemas, developed and used by an active community. This is a flexible tool that works within a web browser without the need for any server-side systems, which makes it very portable.

¹³ The source code is available on GitHub - <https://github.com/jpadfield/dynamic-modelling>

¹⁴ The code is licensed under the [GPL-3.0 licence](https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.html).

¹⁵ The diagram are created using the open source javascript library Mermaid - “... diagramming and charting tool that renders Markdown-inspired text definitions to create and modify diagrams dynamically.” - <https://mermaid-js.github.io>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724103>

¹⁷ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/ASSQXO>

¹⁸ An example template for a generic “object” can be seen in section 13.

¹⁹ <https://github.com/json-editor/json-editor>

The project hosts a simple demo page²⁰ that implements and documents the library for testing purposes, using an object template as an example.²¹ This online tool provides all the functions needed for the proposed T6.3 work, providing an example template, the resultant form, and correctly formatted data output. The system also provides options for data validation and various formatting options and themes.

6.2.2 KIK/IRPA - Form Generator

Based on existing code already in HESCIDA's Metahub,²² which itself implements VJSF, an alternative tool was also tested to facilitate the writing, testing, and sharing JSON schema definitions amongst the partners in this task. By drawing on the previous work within HESCIDA this Form Generator provided a more complete solution based on a simple three step approach: writing JSON schema, visualising and evaluating the generated form and evaluating the resulting JSON data. Each of those steps has its own tab in the tool.

- The first tab consists of a JSON schema editor with JSON syntax highlighting and validation. In addition, all pre-existing schemas stored in the GitHub repository for IPERION HS T6.3 can be selected from a dropdown list.²³
- The second tab shows the webform²⁴ that is responsively generated based on the given schema. This implements the VJSF library to present the created forms. This form thus visualises the schema and can be used to evaluate it.
- Any data entered in the form, or data predefined in the schema, will be formatted in a JSON instance of the form data, which can be evaluated on the third tab.

The JSON Schema Form Generator tool is available online²⁵ and the source code²⁶ is freely available under the *MIT licence*.

6.2.3 Editor Comparison

Initial tests with the JSON Editor demo tool went well but further customisation and some development work would be required to create a complete service for the project rather than a generic tool.

Both editors worked well and can generate forms directly from the same JSON templates, see Figure 8 - both options include additional but different options to define further formatting options.

Due to the planned ongoing development work of the KIK/IRPA tool and the overlapping goals and activities of HESCIDA and T6.3 the decision was made to progress with the KIK/IRPA tool. However, it should be noted that the important issue here, for future exploitation, is the use of the agreed JSON templates, to structure and gather consistent and thus interoperable data, rather than a specific editor. As noted, the KIK/IRPA tool has been released under an open MIT licence so it can

²⁰ A demonstration of the form created from a simple "object" template can be seen at: <https://research.ng-london.org.uk/je/object.html> - a screen shot of the resultant form can be seen in Figure 8.

²¹ The initial draft "object" template has been added as an appendix to this document and can be seen in section 13.1.

²² HESCIDA (<http://hescida.kikirpa.be>) and the Metahub are described in more detail in section 7.2.

²³ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/External%20Models/HESCIDA>

²⁴ A screenshot of the form created from a simple "object" template can be seen in Figure 6.

²⁵ <https://bytes.kikirpa.be/form-generator>

²⁶ The (MIT licensed) source code is available on GitHub - <https://github.com/KIKIRPA/form-generator>

be reused within other documentation systems, but if needed other solutions based on alternative open-source libraries can be used to create data in the same structured format.²⁷

Figure 8: A comparison of the two form automatically generated by the two tools discussed in section 6.2. The form on the left was created using the JSON Editor and the form on the right was created using the KIK/IRPA - Form Generator. Both forms were automatically created based on the example “object” template shown in section 13.

7 External Ontologies and Resources

Interoperability is rooted in the use of shared standards and formats, so T6.3 is making use of and being guided by existing standards where appropriate. In this section we describe some of the existing resources and ontologies that are already being used or considered within the work of T6.3: the CIDOC CRM ontology and its extension *SSHOCro*, along with work from the ongoing HESCIDA project and the already finished PARTHENOS project, with a focus on how our models are and will be informed by these ontologies and resources. CIDOC CRM provides a high-level model of how to look at things and our models will be informed by the basic event driven concepts of the CIDOC CRM. While we do not attempt full compatibility with CIDOC CRM at this stage, we will provide a few sample mappings to CIDOC CRM. The HESCIDA project has already done some modelling work

²⁷ Institutions that would like to make use of the proposed JSON templates based approach, but already have existing digital documentation systems, might need to select alternative open source libraries that will more readily integrate with their current software.

and has some concrete results. The PARTHENOS project has created some tools that have proven useful for this task.

7.1 CIDOC CRM

CIDOC CRM²⁸ is a high-level ontology for the cultural heritage that is increasingly used to also model heritage science data. It sees the world as a series of events, i.e. meetings of people, ideas and objects, which interact with each other in limited areas of space and time and bring about noteworthy changes. It defines a controlled hierarchical list of types (“classes”) of things and the relationships they can have with other things (“properties”). It is extensively documented and has been used in a wide range of heritage related research projects.^{28,29,30} It employs a strict bottom-up approach, which means it is always based on real data to be modelled.

Statements in CIDOC CRM, as with other formal ontologies, in general consist of one or more simple “subject predicate³¹ object” sentences, where the object of one sentence is the subject of the next sentence. For example, an architrave is a lintel that rests on the capitals of columns. A statement like “the architrave dates from the 3rd century BC” may be expressed more formally as “the production of the architrave took place at some unknown time somewhere in the 3rd century BC”, which would look more like this in a formal ontology (a “colloquial version” of CIDOC CRM):

Subject (class)	Predicate (property)	Object (class)
Human-Made Object "Architrave"	was produced by	Production (i.e. the production event of this architrave)
Production (i.e. the production event of this architrave)	has time-span	Time-Span (denoting the exact time, which is unknown)
Time-Span (denoting the exact time, which is unknown)	falls within	Time-Span "3rd century CE"

Table 3: A simple example set of “subject predicate object” triples linking and Architrave to its date of production.

This “subject predicate object” structure can be implemented or formatted in different frameworks. The most popular framework is *RDF*.

7.1.1 SSHOCro

SSHOCro³² is a CIDOC CRM extension that was developed within SSHOC and is still under development. It models the lifecycle of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) data and extends the reach of CIDOC CRM into the social sciences.

²⁸ <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

²⁹ Joseph Padfield. (2019). D.8.5 Completed example of prototype designs for integration of various types of documentation and analytical data generated for a single object (1.0). Deliverable EU H2020 IPERION CH – GA n. 654028. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5519016>

³⁰ Joseph Padfield, Orla Delaney, & Anna Amat Alberti. (2022). D5.16 Report on making heritage science data FAIR (Open data in Heritage Science and Archaeology) (v1.0). Deliverable Eu H2020 SSHOC - GA n. 823782 . <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6779594>

³¹ The predicate can also be described as the “verb” or “property”.

³² <https://isl.ics.forth.gr/SSHOCro/>

The basic concepts of SSHOCro are Project (with a project status and a work plan), Dataset, Service / Tool and a range of project activities. The main project activities are “Knowledge Workflow Activities” (KWA), which model an assumed common order of work steps in scientific research, namely (1) Data Collection, (2) Data Preparation, i.e. processing datasets and connecting different datasets, and (3) Interpretation, which includes every recorded decision up to writing whole reports. The KWA are complemented by two auxiliary activities, namely Data Storage and Publication (of data, reports etc.).

There are two main reasons to examine SSHOCro in more detail. First, although SSHOCro is meant for SSH projects, its creators have themselves applied it to Heritage Science projects and data, and mapped *Raman* spectroscopy data to CIDOC CRM / SSHOCro. We will evaluate this mapping, in relation to the IPERION HS DMP workflow diagram, see Figure 5, particularly testing whether the suggested common Knowledge Workflow Activity step order “collection-processing-interpretation” is a good fit for the concrete work steps common in heritage science research. We will also evaluate whether the SSHOCro Raman mapping also works for the HESCIDA Raman schema, which would be an indication that SSHOCro is also applicable to other kinds of Heritage Science data.

Second, tracking the provenance of data is an important step for creating trust in the data. SSHOCro aims to provide a framework for tracking data provenance based on the Knowledge Workflow Activity steps. We aim to evaluate this approach and compare it with an alternative where the data provenance is not tracked by Knowledge Workflow Activities themselves but instead by their dataset inputs and outputs.

7.2 HESCIDA

HESCIDA³³ is an *E-RIHS.be* project led by KIK/IRPA that aims to create a heritage science knowledge base with art historical, conservation/restoration and material data. The activities of this ongoing project show a large overlap with the activities of IPERION HS T6.3. It makes sense for both projects to work together intensively, for example in the development of common metadata schemas.

HESCIDA builds on the existing *BALaT* portal³⁴ which currently presents a unique collection of over 850 000 photos of Belgian heritage, an authority list of persons & institutions, and the library catalogue. A vast treasure of archives remain however undisclosed: almost 20 000 intervention files since the inception of KIK/IRPA in 1948 contain evidence of a rich past and present in the research and treatment of numerous heritage objects: condition, conservation, restoration and laboratory reports, detailed images taken during restoration, samples, analytical data, etc. HESCIDA aims to disclose these valuable datasets in BALaT and a repository.

The HESCIDA stack will include Metahub,³⁵ a bespoke and open-source documentation platform for intervention files, reports, analytical datasets, samples, and sample collections. Resources in Metahub will be linked to other resources in Metahub and in other data stores in the HESCIDA stack (objects in the collection management system, photos in the IIF service, researchers, etc.).

Due to the widely differing metadata that needs to be stored in Metahub and the need to create a user-friendly environment for the researchers, a versatile mechanism is implemented. The platform has four basic core models: projects, datasets (reports, scientific imaging, analytical data), samples

³³ <http://hescida.kikirpa.be>

³⁴ <http://balat.kikirpa.be>

³⁵ The (MIT licensed) source code is available on GitHub - <https://github.com/KIKIRPA/metahub>

and sample collections. Each of those core models only contain the most rudimentary metadata that is required for the proper functioning of the software and are subsequently extended in two tiers to cater for specific needs.

The first tier, “categories”, are meant to define universal metadata schemas. An example of this would be metadata schema for a Raman spectroscopy measurement. The second tier, “templates”, are used to define very specific schemas, in which many metadata fields are predefined or limited to a specific set-up in a specific lab. An example of this could be a metadata schema for a Raman spectroscopy experiment conducted with the Renishaw InVia, equipped with a NIR 785nm laser. This aids the researcher in quickly and correctly filling in the metadata and reducing the repetitive entry of identical data.

Metadata schemas in Metahub are defined as JSON schema files. The HESCIDA team is currently in the process of developing JSON schema files for all resources that will be documented in Metahub.

There is of course a very large overlap with the resources to be described in the access platforms in IPERION HS and the future research infrastructure, as well as with the resources in similar labs. Drafts of the HESCIDA metadata schemas are (and will continue to be) deposited in the GitHub repository for IPERION HS T6.3.³⁶ The aim is to streamline and standardise the various models based on cross-learning.

At the time of writing, metadata schemas were posted for Raman spectroscopy, dendrochronology and drilling resistance measurements.

7.3 PARTHENOS Spreadsheets

The questions put in focus when setting the work plan for this task, represents a common concern in the Heritage Science community and the work developed in T6.3 is meant to be a continuation and intensification of efforts initiated in previous joint projects. The PARTHENOS project, completed in October 2019, is a very good example of this. It aimed to strengthening the cohesion of research in the broad sector of Linguistic Studies, Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology and related fields and build bridges between different, although tightly interrelated, fields. The PARTHENOS approach to achieve this objective was set through the definition and support of common standards, the coordination of joint activities, the harmonisation of policy definition and implementation, and the development of pooled services and of shared solutions to the same problems.

Modelling the documentation of analytical protocols and respective instrumental parameters, used in each measurement instance, requires the exchange and agreement among specialists, for each separate technique. This essential step corresponding to stages 1 and 2 in our work plan has been already accomplished for a few analytical techniques (spectroscopic techniques for materials investigation), thanks to domain experts’ collaborative work in the framework of the PARTHENOS project. Such models, which were available as spreadsheets, were used in this task as a starting point for developing them further according to the stages in our outlined interoperability process. These PARTHENOS spreadsheets also indicate how the gathered metadata could be mapped to the CIDOC CRM (and compatible models) to formulate relevant information on the analytical protocols, related projects, analytical or conservation campaigns and heritage objects involved in a structured manner compatible with information systems. This additional information can also be exploited in

³⁶ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/External%20Models/HESCIDA>

the future when the development of the T6.3 models reaches the final 8th stage, when they can also be mapped to the CIDOC CRM.

In parallel, these models served to generate, through iterative steps of abstraction and generalisation, a common scheme of documentation and a metadata structure adaptable to different analytical protocols and procedures. This consistent standard/template structure, which could be followed for each protocol or procedure, increases interoperability, and enables the exchange of information in the future. Within T6.3 this approach is being exploited as a template to build models for similar techniques.

8 Developed General Shared Models

Handling and sharing data related to IPERION HS activities will require specific data models to be developed to ensure that all the appropriate metadata is recorded for specific techniques and procedures. However, there are several parts of the research data life cycle that can rely on common models, defining shared or reused data. For example, we should not need to redefine or record the metadata for the IPERION HS project for every access. Details and links for some of the example draft, shared, models are given in Table 4. Improved versions of these models will be added to the GitHub repository as they are developed within T6.3.³⁷

Model	Description	Version
Equipment ³⁸	A specific piece of analytical or examination equipment with defined detectors, Model Numbers, Working distances etc.	1.0
Measurement	An individual analytical measurement, with reference to relevance techniques, equipment, experimental conditions, etc.	0.1
Object	A broad possible range of heritage collection objects, such as paintings, sculpture, books, archaeological stone, etc.	1.1
Range/Dimension	An initial draft of how actual numerical values can be recorded to define the ranges, targets or settings required for pieces of analytical equipment.	1.0
Service	A service represents the situation where access to a particular technique, using a specific piece or set up of equipment, following a defined, consistent series or processes or procedures is made available for researchers.	0.1
Technique	A general analytical or examination technique used to study heritage collection objects or mock-ups, materials, etc.- such as Raman, Reflectance Spectroscopy, GC-MS, etc.	2.1

Table 4: Details and links for the initial draft shared models that have been created within T6.3.

³⁷ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/Shared%20Models>

³⁸ An example of this simple model can be seen in Figure 2.

Once these shared models have been finalised and tested, they will be used to generate JSON schema templates to facilitate future data entry.

9 Developed Detailed Models

9.1 Reflectance Spectroscopy - Artificial Ageing

Diffuse Reflectance spectroscopy is a common technique for the characterization of colouring materials as dyestuffs, inks, paints and pigments, based on their optical properties. The method utilises spectral differences between incident and backscattered light intensity for quantifying the underlying absorption and scattering processes that affect the light-material interaction on the surface. When used complementarily with techniques providing higher analytical specificity performance, it may also be applied to materials identification. As for most analytical techniques, the instrumental setup for applying reflectance spectroscopy may vary significantly at several levels as the type of probe, the spot size, the working distance, the type of detector, the spectral range, the spectral resolution etc. can all vary. Therefore, for sharing, comparing or exploiting data produced with different equipment and respective instrumental setups, a core set of metadata is indispensable to document these differences and to put the stored datasets in context.

Because diffuse reflectance spectroscopy is being applied by a group of specialists involved in IPERION HS JRA Task 5.1, on replicas of the same set of mock-ups, but applying different accelerated ageing protocols and employing different equipment and different types of light sources, it was considered as a perfect candidate, for the parallel T6.3, to assess the efficiency of our interoperability approach throughout all its stages. The method is used by IPERION HS partners for the detection and monitoring of colour/chemical change of pigments under the effect of accelerated photo-ageing procedures and the acquired data will be, in addition, assessed comparatively with Microfading test (*MFT*) data also produced in the same task. An ultimate aim is to explore all data together, for assessing, validating, or disproving or improving existing or developing new models of material damage functions that are of high importance in Preventive Conservation approaches, for preventing light-induced damage of colours.

Before starting their measurements, the specialists spent time and effort to define and agree on common schemas for the documentation of the data produced and agree on the core set of metadata required to document the equipment specs and instrumental, measurement conditions followed by each lab, and each examination workflow referring, in particular, to the metadata models of “technique” and “measurement”. The respective metadata schemas were designed to assure that the data acquired during the project will respect FAIR principles and will, after all, assure sharing, comparative interpretation and integration of data acquired either with light-induced accelerated ageing monitored with diffuse reflectance measurements or MFT measurements even when captured using different analytical protocols, equipment specs or instrumental measurement conditions.

Up to now, exchange among partners on the metadata schema has been carried out using a spreadsheet file format, see section 13.2, but the creation and update of the metadata templates in JSON format is planned.

9.2 Raman Spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy is an established analytical technique for the characterisation of a wide range of inorganic and organic materials in heritage science: pigments, dyes, polymers, mortars, salts, etc. A schema was developed within the HESCIDA project, based on the existing work of the Infrared & Raman Users Group (IRUG).³⁹ In addition, Raman spectroscopy is listed in the IPERION HS catalogue of services². Therefore, it was selected as an example to be worked out within this task.

The technique is based on the inelastic scattering of photons (“Raman scattering”), induced by a monochromatic light, usually a laser. The laser light interacts with molecular vibrations, resulting in the energy of the laser photons being shifted up or down. The shift in energy in the scattered light gives information about the vibrational modes in the sample. In many materials, this provides a structural fingerprint by which molecules can be identified. It gives complementary information to the related FTIR technique and to elementary characterisation techniques such as XRF and EDX.

A wide variety of instrumental set-ups and instrumental parameters exist: dispersive or transformation-based instruments, microscope-based and/or glass fibre probe-coupled systems, different laser wavelengths, etc. Knowledge of these parameters is important when comparing spectra obtained with different systems, since these may have a major influence on the spectra.

The IRUG is a community that encourages the sharing of high-quality comparative reference spectral data in heritage science, both for FTIR and Raman spectroscopy. IRUG collects FTIR and Raman reference spectra for the study of works of art, architecture and archaeological materials, and offers their peer-reviewed database through their website (open for all) and for download (to contributors only). IRUG uses an extended and standardised form of the open and human-readable *JCAMP-DX* format for documenting and sharing spectra.⁴⁰ IRUG has added a large number of labelled, data records and instructions to extensively document Raman and FTIR spectra of heritage science reference materials.

In the framework of HESCIDA, a JSON schema was made. This schema was heavily influenced by the IRUG metadata specifications. Conversion to/from their JCAMP-DX format should be straightforward and easy to automate. Some aspects from the IRUG specifications describe the sample and its origin, with a strong focus on reference materials and therefore not always usable to describe samples of heritage objects or for measurements performed directly on the objects. Detailed sample metadata was therefore not included and will become a linked resource; only the reference to a sample is captured in the Raman schema.

The generic Raman schema,⁴¹ shown in section 13.3, as developed in the HESCIDA project has been posted on the GitHub E-RIHS HS-interoperability workspace under “External models”. A derivative schema “raman_invia785”⁴² was created as an example schema for a specific frequently used set-up at KIK/IRPA in which a number of metadata values are predefined (e.g. instrument: Renishaw

³⁹ <http://www.irug.org>

⁴⁰ Beth A. Price, Boris Pretzel, Suzanne Quillen Lomax, Charles Davis, Janice H. Carlson. “Revised JCAMP-DX Spectral File Format for Submissions to the Infrared & Raman Users Group (IRUG) Spectral Database”, 2013. <http://irug.org/uploads/documentation/irug-jcamp-dx-revised-white-paper-text-only-with-2b-version-1-26-sept-2013.pdf>

⁴¹ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/blob/main/External%20Models/HESCIDA/raman.schema.json>

⁴² https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/blob/main/External%20Models/HESCIDA/raman_invia785.schema.json

InVia) and other metadata restricted to a selectable list of predefined values (e.g. a list with the objective lenses that are available on this system).

10 Conclusions

Improving the interoperability of Heritage Science research is a complex process that requires the contributions and consensus from a wide range of specialists. It can take considerable expertise to achieve, but when we start considering Heritage Science research on a European or even Global scale, without good documentation and all the required metadata and paradata we risk losing much of the context and meaning of the work being done. However, even though it is generally accepted that good levels of documentation and the use of open and standard formats is key, capturing all the required metadata and paradata can be very time consuming. It is important to ensure that these specialists can see the process as being realistic and ultimately useful. It is also important to consider that interoperability can be tackled on many different levels, and that all improvements can be beneficial.

To ensure that the work is practical and useful, it needs to be a collaboration between domain experts and knowledge/semantic experts. Exploiting efficient and accessible systems to capture the required level of knowledge in a reusable form.

In relation to projects like IPERION HS and the future E-RIHS initiative, ideally the work needs to aim to develop the potential of all the digital resources created rather than focusing too much on single techniques. However, we do need to start somewhere, but as long as the approaches taken are open and flexible, then the initial work can be replicated, updated and developed to fit other situations and other forms of examinations.

T6.3 has therefore aimed at developing the process of achieving improved interoperability, proposing and developing a relatively simple and very accessible method based on open standard technologies. Which involves creating simple linked data models, using tab separated text documents, linked to standard JSON schema templates and automatically generated data entry forms. This approach is very flexible and scalable, it could be implemented in a wide variety of ways, via simple local web pages on one's own laptop right up to being integrated into complex multiuser online digital documentation systems.

Once a few fully worked up analysis/examination examples have been created, linked to a wide range of re-usable shared models, it becomes much simpler for less technical experts to create models for their own work. This could then allow individual IPERION HS service providers to adapt the examples to create their own models and form templates describing their own methods and procedures.

The goal is not to force all analysis, using a given technique, to be done following a single “standard” method. It is to ensure that all researchers use consistent and agreed approaches to document what is being done, making use of agreed and appropriate standard tools and formats, to an agreed consistent level. Thus, ensuring that future researchers can understand the context of the work and the results can be appropriately re-used and compared.

11 Recommendations

In addition to the reported work, the activities and discussions within T6.3 have also raised the following eight recommendations:

1. A better understanding of the benefits of DMPs needs to be developed across the IPERION HS project, to ensure that they can be seen as useful tools rather than just additional documentation.
2. As indicated in the work of this task, where possible, developments in interoperability should aim to be practical and inclusive, providing real options and solutions for practitioners. This can ensure that the developments can be more easily integrated into ongoing research work and help to enact improvements within documentation and data management within the field.
3. Once the work on the “detailed models” is a bit more advanced it would be good to organise a user meeting - to allow service providers to test and work through the process of modelling their work. The aim of this meeting would be to develop an accessible guide to the process and generate some additional worked examples. Potentially creating a blueprint for future training opportunities.
4. It is strongly recommended that a metadata model will need to be created for every type of service in the catalogue of services and that will only be possible with the direct involvement of service providers to ensure that the metadata needs of their techniques and procedures are captured.
5. It is recommended that the “Levels of interoperability” included in this report be examined and tested by the wider community and edited as required to provide an agreed basis on which the current or planned interoperability of institutions or service providers can be compared.
6. All analytical techniques may not allow or even benefit from the same levels of interoperability. It is recommended that an interoperability matrix is developed, based on the catalogue of service, where domain experts can indicate useful and practical levels of interoperability for their specialty.
7. It is recommended that details of any related work being carried out by service providers and institutions involved in the wider E-RIHS community be listed within the E-RIHS GitHub repository (<https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability>) to ensure that a clear consensus relating to “best-practice” in relation to documentation, data management and interoperability can be developed.
8. It is also recommended that other interested researchers, within IPERION HS and those working in the wider Heritage Science community, engage with the open GitHub repository, posting questions (<https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/issues>) as required and even contribute work where appropriate.

12 IPERION HS response to Recommendations

13 Appendices

13.1 Appendix A: An example Object JSON Schema Template.

This is an example of the initial draft JSON schema template generated for Heritage Science collection objects. It was used to create the example forms shown in Figure 8.

```
{
  "title": "Object",
  "type": "object",
  "required": [
    "identifier",
    "title"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "title": {
      "type": "string",
      "title": "Title",
      "options": {
        "infoText": "The main title of the Object - the principal
        denomination with which the art work or monument is currently
        known"
      },
      "default": ""
    },
    "shortTitle": {
      "type": "string",
      "title": "Short Title",
      "options": {
        "infoText": "Optional Short presentation title"
      }
    },
    "shortDescription": {
      "type": "string",
      "title": "Short Description",
      "format": "textarea",
      "options": {
        "infoText": "A brief text describing the object"
      },
      "default": "Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text ...."
    },
    "objectDescription": {
      "type": "string",
      "format": "textarea",
      "title": "Object Description",
      "options": {
        "infoText": "A detailed description of the Object"
      },
      "default": "Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text ..."
    },
    "currentLocation": {
      "type": "string",
      "title": "Current Location",
      "options": {
        "infoText": "PID for the current location"
      },
      "default": "0000-0000-0000-0000"
    },
    "permissions": {
      "type": "string",
      "title": "Permissions",
      "format": "url",
      "options": {
        "infoText": "This may be a type or controlled list values or an URL
        to a relevant resource - Needs to define details of what can/can not
        be done to the object including licences etc."
      },
      "default": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/"
    }
  }
}
```

```
},
"identifier": {
  "type": "array",
  "format": "table",
  "options": {
    "infoText": "URL or Text values defining the various identifiers
    linked to the object - It is expected that we will need at least 2-3
    identifiers for each object: The owners own identifier, an external
    resolvable PID (if available) and a local E-RIHS PID."
  },
  "title": "Identifiers",
  "uniqueItems": true,
  "items": {
    "type": "object",
    "title": "Identifier",
    "properties": {
      "which": {
        "type": "string",
        "enum": [
          "PID",
          "Inv. No.",
          "E-RIHS PID",
          "other"
        ],
        "default": "PID"
      },
      "value": {
        "type": "string"
      }
    },
    "default": [
      {
        "value": "0000-0000-0000-0000"
      }
    ]
  },
  "dimension": {
    "type": "array",
    "format": "table",
    "options": {
      "infoText": "Objects can have multiple dimensions - and each will
      have a defined Type, Value and Unit. Types and Units will be
      Vocabulary terms"
    },
    "title": "Dimensions",
    "uniqueItems": true,
    "items": {
      "type": "object",
      "title": "Dimension",
      "properties": {
        "type": {
          "type": "string",
          "enum": [
            "height",
            "width",
            "depth",
            "weight",
            "other"
          ],
          "default": "height"
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```



```

    },
    "value": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "unit": {
      "type": "string",
      "enum": [
        "cm",
        "mm",
        "kg",
        "g",
        "other"
      ],
      "default": "cm"
    }
  },
  "default": [
    {
      "value": "120"
    }
  ],
  "event": {
    "type": "array",
    "format": "table",
    "title": "Events",
    "options": {
      "infoText": "Contains a reference to information about related event(s), the default being a creation event and creator(s) details for the object - PID - Linked to event details entered separately"
    },
    "uniqueltems": true,
    "items": {
      "type": "object",
      "title": "Event",
      "properties": {
        "which": {
          "type": "string",
          "enum": [
            "creation",
            "exhibition",
            "damage",
            "examination",
            "conservation",
            "other"
          ],
          "default": "creation"
        },
        "value": {
          "type": "string"
        }
      },
      "default": [
        {
          "value": "0000-0000-0000-0000"
        }
      ],
      "currentOwner": {
        "type": "array",
        "format": "table",
        "title": "Current Owner",
        "options": {
          "infoText": "Contains information about the current owner of the object, including details of Institutions or People - PID - linked to details entered separately."
        },
        "uniqueltems": true,

```

```

"items": {
  "type": "object",
  "title": "Owner",
  "properties": {
    "Owner ID": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "Comment": {
      "type": "string"
    }
  }
},
"objectCategories": {
  "type": "array",
  "format": "table",
  "title": "Object Categories",
  "options": {
    "infoText": "The type(s) or category(s) for the Object - ideally a controlled list connected to defined vocabulary terms."
  },
  "uniqueltems": true,
  "items": {
    "type": "object",
    "title": "Category",
    "properties": {
      "objectCategory": {
        "type": "string",
        "title": "Category",
        "enum": [
          "painting",
          "drawing",
          "sculpture",
          "book",
          "other"
        ],
        "default": "bronze"
      }
    }
  },
"materialCategories": {
  "type": "array",
  "format": "table",
  "title": "Material Categories",
  "options": {
    "infoText": "The main type(s) or category(s) used to define the materials used to create the Object - ideally a controlled list connected to defined vocabulary terms."
  },
  "uniqueltems": true,
  "items": {
    "type": "object",
    "title": "Category",
    "properties": {
      "materialCategory": {
        "type": "string",
        "title": "Category",
        "enum": [
          "copper",
          "bronze",
          "steel",
          "iron",
          "other"
        ],
        "default": "bronze"
      }
    }
  }
},

```



```

"materials": {
  "type": "array",
  "format": "table",
  "title": "Identified Materials",
  "options": {
    "infoText": "A list of all of the specific materials that have been
identified with the object - ideally a controlled list connected to
defined vocabulary terms."
  },
  "uniqueltems": true,
  "items": {
    "type": "object",
    "title": "Material",
    "properties": {
      "material": {
        "type": "string",
        "title": "Material",
        "enum": [
          "Gypsum",
          "linseed oil",
          "Canvas",
          "Gilding",
          "Sulphate",
          "other"
        ],
        "default": "bronze"
      }
    }
  }
},
"examinations": {
  "type": "array",
  "format": "table",
  "title": "Examinations",
  "options": {
    "infoText": "A list of all of the previous examinations and
analytical techniques used to study the object and relevant samples -
ideally a controlled list connected to defined vocabulary terms."
  },
  "uniqueltems": true,
  "items": {
    "type": "object",

```

```

"title": "Examination",
"properties": {
  "examinedWith": {
    "type": "string",
    "title": "Examination",
    "enum": [
      "X-ray",
      "HSI",
      "IR",
      "GC-MS",
      "other"
    ],
    "default": "bronze"
  }
}
},
"references": {
  "type": "array",
  "format": "table",
  "title": "Bibliography",
  "options": {
    "infoText": " A list of all of the identified references relating to
the examination and or study of the object - ideally a list of DOIs or
similar resolvable PIDs."
  },
  "uniqueltems": true,
  "items": {
    "type": "object",
    "title": "Reference",
    "properties": {
      "link": {
        "type": "string",
        "format": "URL"
      }
    }
  }
}
}
}
}

```


13.2 Appendix B: Screenshot of an example PARTHENOS spreadsheet.

This is an example screenshot of part of one of the initial PARTHENOS spreadsheets used to capture the detailed metadata required needed to describe diffuse reflectance spectroscopy:

Monitoring accelerated ageing process with Diffuse Reflectance spectroscopy_metadata_template-chrome yellow .xlsx

File Edit View Insert Format Data Tools Help Last edit was made 3 days ago by Sophia Sotiriopoulou

	A	B	C
10		3.Owner of the object / Scholar - keeper:	<CurrentOwner> contains information about the current owner of the object
11		4.Date/period: Information about the date	<CreationInformation> contains information about the creation of the object
12		5.Type of object: Information about the type of the object such as polychromy on sculpture, panel painting etc.	<ObjectCategory>: the type or category of the Object
13		6.Type of material(s) for examination: Type(s) of materials for examination, e.g. substrate, coatings, pigments or other materials related to surface	<MaterialCategory> contains information about the type of materials under investigation
14	Describe the project	1. Framework, analytical context (motivation - aim of the analytical campaign); Short presentation of the main objectives of the analysis of the artworks/monument	<Identity of the project> information about the project in which the object is investigated, or
15			<Project Title>: the title of the Project - framework
16			<Project ID>
17			<Project Type>: the type of the Project
18			<Project Goal>: the goal of the project
19		2. Describe the project workflow: radiation/light-induced accelerated ageing experiment/test	<LightSource>: the type of lighting source used for the aging experiment (e.g. xenon lamp, halogen lamp, LEDs light, monochromatic source...) <Filter>: the type of filter used for modulating the emission spectral profile of the light source <nominalpower>: the power value expressed in W provided from the manufacturer <spectralirradiance>: the irradiance value expressed in W·m ⁻² measured at the sample's position <illuminance>: the illuminance value expressed in lux measured at the sample's position <Irradiatedarea>: the spot size of the lighting source <exposuretime>: the total exposure time <equivalentexposuretime>: the time (in years) of natural ageing to which the artificial ageing is considered equivalent <temperature>: the average temperature value measured at the sample's position over the irradiation experiment <relativehumidity>: the average relative humidity percentage value measured during the irradiation experiment
20		3. Preliminary analysis: Information about any preliminary visual examination or previous analysis on the same measurement sites	<MacroscopicExamination> (or <Observation>) contains information about the condition of the object as observed without the use of devices <RelatedTechnicalExamination> includes information of the related Technical examination that was preliminary applied to the Object during the specific Project <Method 1> the name of the Technical Examination
21		(Possible source or error: wrong selection	

D	E
/	E 39 Actor - E 40 Legal body or F10 Person: P105B has right on: E22 Physical Man-made object.
/	E22 Physical Man-made object. P105 was produced by:E12 Production: P117 occurred during: E4
paint mock-up	E22 Physical Man-made object - P2 has type: E55 Type (e.g. Painting)
chrome yellow (PbCr0.2S0.8O4) mixed with linseed oil (pigment: binder weight ratio=4:1) on polycarbonate support	E22 Physical Man-made object: P46 is composed of: E18 Physical Thing P57 has number of parts: E60 Number P45 consists of: E57 Material P44 has condition: E3 Condition State
Chemical/color changes induced by accelerated photoaging experiments	E7 Activity: P1 is identified by: E41 Appellation E7 Activity: P4 has time-span: E52 Timespan P2 has type: E55 Type E7 Activity: P21 had general purpose: E55 Type E7 Activity: P17 was motivated by: E1 CRM Entity E7 Activity: P70B is documented in: E31 Document
Research project	
Assessment of the consequences of the visible light on the photoredox pathways of chrome yellow pigments in the oil medium	
/	
/	
xenon lamp (Cermax)	
soda-lime glass	
150 W	
3.2x103 W·m ⁻²	
1.72x105 lux	
/	
114 h	
ca. 30 years	
25-30 °C	
40-45%	
see comment	E7 Activity: P2 has type: E55 type S4 Observation
not applicable	E7 Activity: P2 has type:E55 type E7 Activity: P33 used specific technique: E29 Design or Procedure : P69 has association with: E29 Design or Procedure E29 Design or Procedure: P67B is referred to by: E73 Information Object

13.3 Appendix C: An example HESCIDA project, generic, Raman schema

This is an example JSON schema template provided by the HESCIDA project, describing a generic example of Raman Spectroscopy:

```
{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "$id": "https://balat.kikirpa.be/schema/dataset/raman",
  "title": "Raman spectroscopy",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "id": {
      "title": "Id",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "dataset_code": {
      "title": "Dataset Code",
      "description": "Dataset code",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "project": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/Project"
    },
    "object_id": {
      "title": "Object Id",
      "description": "Object number to which this dataset belongs",
      "type": "integer"
    },
    "samples": {
      "title": "Samples",
      "type": "array",
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/Sample"
      }
    },
    "contributors": {
      "title": "Contributors",
      "type": "array",
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/Contributor"
      },
      "uniqueItems": true
    },
    "terms": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/Terms"
    },
    "persistent_identifier": {
      "title": "Persistent Identifier",
      "description": "Persistent identifier for the dataset",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "files": {
      "title": "Files",
      "type": "array",
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/File"
      }
    },
    "created_timestamp": {
      "title": "Created Timestamp",
      "type": "string",
      "format": "date-time"
    },
    "created_by_user": {
      "title": "Created By User",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "modified_timestamp": {
      "title": "Modified Timestamp",
```

```

      "type": "string",
      "format": "date-time"
    },
    "modified_by_user": {
      "title": "Modified By User",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "measurement_parameters": {
      "title": "Measurement parameters",
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "instrument": {
          "title": "Instrument",
          "description": "Spectrometer manufacturer and model",
          "type": "string"
        },
        "software": {
          "title": "Software",
          "description": "Acquisition and data treatment software used",
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "type": "string"
          },
          "uniqueItems": true
        },
        "detector_type": {
          "title": "Detector Type",
          "description": "Type of detector",
          "type": "string",
          "enum": [
            "CCD",
            "InGaAs"
          ]
        },
        "spectrometer_class": {
          "title": "Spectrometer Class",
          "description": "Spectrometer Class (dispersive, FT)",
          "type": "string",
          "enum": [
            "dispersive",
            "FT"
          ]
        },
        "accessories": {
          "title": "Accessories",
          "description": "Name and model of accessories",
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "type": "string"
          },
          "uniqueItems": true
        },
        "excitation_source_wavelength": {
          "title": "Excitation Source Wavelength",
          "description": "Laser line wavelength in nanometers (nm)",
          "type": "number"
        },
        "laser_power": {
          "title": "Laser power",
          "type": "object",
          "properties": {
            "laser_power_at_sample": {
```

```

    "title": "Laser Power At Sample",
    "description": "Laser power at sample in mW",
    "type": "number"
  },
  "neutral_density_filtering": {
    "title": "Neutral Density Filtering",
    "description": "Laser power reduction by neutral
density filters expressed in %",
    "type": "number"
  }
},
"spectral_range": {
  "title": "Spectral range",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "spectral_range_low": {
      "title": "Spectral Range Low",
      "description": "Lowest value of the spectral range
expressed in Raman shift (1/cm)",
      "type": "number"
    },
    "spectral_range_high": {
      "title": "Spectral Range High",
      "description": "Highest value of the spectral range
expressed in Raman shift (1/cm)",
      "type": "number"
    }
  }
},
"rejection_filters": {
  "title": "Rejection filters",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "filter_type": {
      "title": "Filter Type",
      "description": "Optical filters used to prevent stray
light from reaching spectrometer/detector",
      "type": "string"
    }
  }
},
"cutoff_frequency": {
  "title": "Cutoff Frequency",
  "description": "Low frequency cut-off in 1/cm",
  "type": "number"
}
},
"grating": {
  "title": "Grating",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "grating_type": {
      "title": "Grating Type",
      "description": "Type of grating",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "grating_density": {
      "title": "Grating Density",
      "description": "Line density of grating in dispersive
Raman instrument in lines/mm",
      "type": "integer"
    }
  }
},
"resolution": {
  "title": "Resolution",
  "description": "Resolution of spectrum as measured in
wavenumbers (1/cm)",
  "type": "number"
},

```

```

    "data_collection": {
      "title": "Data Collection",
      "description": "Raman acquisition mode, static or
scanned",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "integration_time": {
      "title": "Integration Time",
      "description": "Integration or dwell time in seconds",
      "type": "number"
    },
    "accumulations": {
      "title": "Accumulations",
      "description": "Number of accumulations used (co-added)
to produce spectrum",
      "type": "integer"
    },
    "objective": {
      "title": "Objective",
      "description": "Objective lens magnification, numerical
aperture, working distance and series",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "spot_size": {
      "title": "Spot Size",
      "description": "Laser spot diameter (nm) as determined
by laser wavelength and microscope objective. Laser spot diameter =
1.22 (λ)/NA, where λ=wavelength, NA= numerical aperture.",
      "type": "number"
    },
    "confocality": {
      "title": "Confocality",
      "description": "Use of confocal optical arrangement",
      "type": "boolean"
    },
    "laser_defocus": {
      "title": "Laser Defocus",
      "description": "Defocusing of laser",
      "type": "boolean"
    },
    "polarization": {
      "title": "Polarization",
      "description": "Y or N for polarization of excitation
radiation with degrees and orientation followed by Y or N for
polarization of scattered radiation with degrees and orientation
(Example: incident, Y, 45 degrees CCW, scattered, N)",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "data_processing": {
      "title": "Data Processing",
      "description": "Data manipulation",
      "type": "array",
      "items": {
        "type": "string"
      },
      "uniqueItems": true
    }
  }
},
"measurement_results": {
  "title": "Measurement results",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "identified_components": {
      "title": "Identified components",
      "type": "array",
      "items": {
        "type": "string"
      },
      "uniqueItems": true
    }
  }
}

```



```

    },
    "comments": {
      "title": "Comments",
      "description": "Comments with regards to generated
research data",
      "type": "string"
    }
  }
},
"required": [
  "id",
  "dataset_code"
],
"definitions": {
  "Unit": {
    "title": "Unit",
    "description": "An enumeration.",
    "enum": [
      "Painting Lab",
      "Dendrochronology Lab"
    ],
    "type": "string"
  },
  "Project": {
    "title": "Project",
    "type": "object",
    "properties": {
      "project_id": {
        "title": "Project Id",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "project_code": {
        "title": "Project Code",
        "description": "Project code (file number, acronym...)",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "unit": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/Unit"
      }
    }
  },
  "Sample": {
    "title": "Sample",
    "type": "object",
    "properties": {
      "sample_id": {
        "title": "Sample Id",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "sample_code": {
        "title": "Sample Code",
        "description": "Sample code",
        "type": "string"
      }
    }
  },
  "Role": {
    "title": "Role",
    "description": "An enumeration.",
    "enum": [
      "Coordinator",
      "Collaborator",
      "Analyst",
      "Author",
      "Operator",
      "Archivist"
    ],
    "type": "string"
  },
}

```

```

"Contributor": {
  "title": "Contributor",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "contributor_id": {
      "title": "Contributor Id",
      "type": "string"
    }
  },
  "roles": {
    "title": "Roles",
    "type": "array",
    "items": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/Role"
    },
    "uniqueItems": true
  }
},
"required": [
  "contributor_id"
]
},
"Terms": {
  "title": "Terms",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "access": {
      "title": "Access",
      "description": "Access modalities",
      "default": "Public",
      "enum": [
        "Public",
        "Restricted access",
        "Private"
      ],
      "type": "string"
    },
    "license": {
      "title": "License",
      "description": "The license that describes the terms",
      "default": "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY
4.0)",
      "enum": [
        "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY 4.0)",
        "Creative Commons Public Domain (CC0)"
      ],
      "type": "string"
    },
    "embargo": {
      "title": "Embargo",
      "description": "Date on which the imposed embargo
expires",
      "type": "string",
      "format": "date"
    }
  }
},
"File": {
  "title": "File",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "path": {
      "title": "Path",
      "description": "Path to a file or a directory",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "type": {
      "title": "File type",
      "type": "string"
    }
  }
}
}

```



```
"required": [  
  "path"  
]  
}  
}
```